
Research

Assessment of river sand and crushed-rock sand for mortar from eastern Nepal Sub-Himalaya

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Abstract: Construction activities are rapidly conducted in all parts of the country. Most important material in those activities is construction material. Mostly sands from the river are used in construction works, which with excessive mining can create various negative effects in the environment. It is essential to search for the alternative of the river sand, which in this case can be crushed rock sand from medium-to coarse-grained sandstones. Therefore, sands from both river and bedrocks were tested for grain size, shape, composition and physical properties. Comparison of particle size analysis with suitable standard gives suitability of both types of sands for general purpose mortar, floor screeding, plastering and rendering. Crushed rock sands are suitable for general purpose mortar and the river sand are more suitable for floor screeding, plastering and rendering purposes. Crushed-rock sands have slightly less specific gravity, more water absorption value and more organic content than those of the river sands. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of mortar cube made from crushed-rock sand have slightly less strength in 7 days of curing but have slightly greater strength in 28 days of curing than UCS river sands. This makes crushed-rock sands useable in structures requiring strength in long term and can also be an alternative for river sands.

Keywords: River Sand, Crushed-rock Sand, Mortar Cube, Trijuga River, Eastern Nepal

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Introduction

Construction materials are most widely used resources for all construction works. Mortar consists of cement, sand and water in an appropriate proportion. Among all, sand covers most of the total volume contributing to overall strength, workability, drying shrinkage, and appearance of mortar. River sand is used mostly for the preparation of mortar and is also a common ingredient of concrete. Nowadays, apart from the river sand, crushed-rock sands and other artificial sands have also been used [1]. Mining of sands and gravels creates disturbances in habitat of rivers [2]. Excessive exploitation of sand mined from river has negative impacts in the river and adjacent environment [1]. Therefore, some alternative to river sand is to be identified to solve this problem without compromising in strength, workability and other rheological properties of mortar [1]. Replacement of up to 80 percent mortar sand by the river sand increases workability, and strength is more at all replacement levels, which makes mortar sand usable for masonry work [1]. Increase of fines content increases strength and hardness of mortar and increase in clay content retards the setting time

with decrease in consistency [3]. Reduction in void content in concrete and mortar tended to increase hardness and strength [4]. Dust content up to ten percent is beneficial in the case of compressive strength, flexural strength and drying shrinkage [4]. The higher yield stress of the mortars with crushed-rock fine aggregate is believed to mainly originate from the relatively high amounts of fines, which is often found in crushed-rock fine aggregate, which can be the cause of high strength of mortar made with the crushed sand [5]. The water content had to be increased in concretes with crushed sand to reach the same consistency as concretes with river sand. In spite of higher water demand in crushed sand concretes, presence of rock dust helps on coping the bleeding [6]. Studies have shown that crushed-rock sands are more suitable in terms of strength and durability than river sands in mortar [6]. Due to shape of the crushed-rock sand, it gives better compressive strength than the river sand [7]. With the hundred percent of replacement of the river sand by crushed-rock sand, strength criteria can be fully established [8]. Fine aggregate produced using the impact crusher containing 14 percent microfines produces a cement mortar with 28 percent lower absorptivity and 23 percent higher strength than one prepared from using river sand [9]. The concrete with crushed-rock sand performed better than concrete with river sand focusing the point that property of crushed-rock sand is better than that of river sand [10]. It was found that compressive strength increased up to the point where crushed-rock sand replaced river sand up to 60%, but beyond that, the strength decreased [11]. This may be due to the fact that 60 percent replacement of crushed-rock sand shows optimum reaction with optimum filler capacity [12]. Mortar mixes made with sand of various gradation show variation in compressive strength and water absorption [13]. Manufactured sand qualifies to provide alternative to river sand helping maintaining the environment as well as economical balance. Scarcity of river sand at reasonable cost compels to search for alternative material. Manufactured sand has potential to substitute for river sand at reasonable cost [14]. The main purpose of this research are to reveal various engineering properties of river sand and crushed-rock sands from Baruwa–Trijuga area, Eastern Nepal Sub-Himalaya, with their comparison under specific and performance analysis to evaluate the suitability of sands for mortar, and finding whether the crushed-rock sand can be alternative to the river sand for use in mortar.

Research Methodology

2. Materials and Methods

The study area lies in the Udaypur District of the Eastern Nepal about 350 km east of the Kathmandu Valley covering mostly the area of the Trijuga Valley (Fig. 1). The material required for the study consisted of two distinct geological materials, river sand from rivers and sandstone from various sites across the Siwalik Group of rock sequences.

2.1 Sample collection

Samples for both the river sand and the crushed-rock sand were taken from suitable locations (Table 1; Fig. 5).

Ten samples from the bedrock and ten samples from the Trijuga and the Baruwa Rivers were taken (Table 1) for the analysis (Table 2). River sands from the Trijuga and the Baruwa Rivers were sampled by pit sampling technique. From the pit 1m³ volume of sample was taken out and from which sand was separated by sieving it with 4.75 mm sieve.

Loose sandstones of the Middle Siwalik was chosen for sampling, in case of hard samples suitable crushing was done by using pestle. The sample of crushed-rock sand was taken perpendicular to the bedding plane so that representative sample can be taken out. Standard of 0.10 m width by 0.10 m depth was followed. Sample was taken out with the help of chisel and representative sample from those samples was further taken after quartering.

Lithologically, all of the sandstone were yellowish grey in color, medium- to coarse-grained, slightly to moderately weathered, quartz rich and poorly to moderately indurated. All of the river sand samples were sampled from mid bar consisting of gravel and sand. The bedrock of sandstone containing medium- to coarse-grained sandstones had thickness greater than 5 m, and they were selected so that enough material can be quarried for excavation purposes.

2.2 Laboratory analysis

2.2.1 Grading

BS 882: (1985) designation was used to carry out sieve analysis along with fineness modulus was calculated to know fineness or coarseness of the sand. The sample with weight varying from 2.0 kg to 2.5 kg was dried to constant mass at a temperature of 100 degree Celsius. Fineness modulus was calculated by adding total percentages of the materials in the sample that is coarser than each of the sieves and divided by 100. To determine the type of gradation both the values of uniformity coefficient and coefficient of curvature were calculated.

2.2.2 Physical properties

Designation ASTM C128-01 was used to determine these physical properties which are essential in determining its suitability for mortar. About 50 gm of sample passing 5 mm sieve was taken. A pycnometer was taken and was filled with water and weighed (B). The fine aggregate was filled in the pycnometer and remaining part was filled with water (C). The mixture was placed for 24 hours in a stable place. After 24 hours, with the help of cotton cloth saturated surface dry (SSD) mass was taken (S). The aggregate was placed in oven for 24 hours and oven dry weight of the sample was noted (A).

Different parameters were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Saturated surface dry specific gravity } (G_{SSD}) = S/(B+S-C)$$

$$\text{Dry specific gravity } (G_{dry}) = A/(B+S-C)$$

$$\text{Apparent Specific Gravity } (G_{SA}) = A/(B+A-C)$$

$$\text{Water Absorption (WA)} = (S-A)/A * 100\%$$

2.2.3 Organic content

Dichromate oxidation method was used to calculate organic content in sand using revised test by [17]. Chemicals: Potassium Dichromate, Ferrous Ammonium Sulfate, Sulfuric acid, Phosphoric Acid, Sodium Fluoride, and Diphenylamine indicator were used. Potassium Dichromate (1N) was prepared by mixing 49.04 g of potassium dichromate (previously dried for 2 hours at 100° C) into a 1 liter volumetric flask. Ferrous Ammonium Sulfate (0.5N) was prepared by mixing 20 ml sulfuric acid slowly to a 1 liter volumetric flask containing 800 ml deionized water and 196.1 g ferrous ammonium sulfate. Diphenylamine Indicator was prepared by dissolving 0.500 g diphenylamine in 20 ml deionized water, 100 ml sulfuric acid. About 1 gm soil sample was weighed and placed in 500 ml volumetric flask. About 10 ml of 1N potassium dichromate solution was added into the flask. Then about 20 ml of sulfuric acid was added and mixed by gentle rotation for 1 minute, and was kept still for 30 minutes (Fig. 2). After 30 minutes, the solution was diluted to 200 ml by using deionized water. About 10 ml phosphoric acid and 10 drops of diphenylamine indicator was added in the solution. The solution was titrated with 0.5N ferrous ammonium sulfate solution until the color changes from dull green to a turbid blue and the titrating solution was added drop by drop until the end point was reached when the color shifted to a brilliant green. Solution without soil sample was also prepared and titrated in the same manner.

Fig. 1. Solution left for 30 minutes to cool down

Calculation:

$$\text{Organic Matter} = (B-T)N/(\text{Weight of sample taken}) \times 0.76$$

Where,

B = Amount of ferrous sulphate required in blank titration.

T = Amount of ferrous sulphate required in sample titration

S = Strength of ferrous sulphate in blank titration (0.5N)

2.2.4 Microscopic analysis

Binocular microscope was used to determine sphericity, roundness, form, composition, surface texture and surface coating of the sand grains. About 100 particles from each coarse (1.18 mm), medium (0.6 mm) and fine (0.3 mm) fractions with total 300 particles obtained from sieve analysis was taken for microscopic analysis. Shape was estimated visually by using the charts of [18] and [19]. Surface texture was estimated by the level of roughness seen in the grains and surface coating was estimated by the amount of iron coating in the grains. Form of sand grains were visually estimated by estimating a, b and c axis of the grain and correlating with the chart given by [20].

2.2.5 Mortar cube test

Performance analysis for both the river sand and the crushed-rock sand was carried out by calculating the compressive strength of mortar by making mortar cubes mixing with cement by using designation ASTM C109/C199M. The materials used for making mortar cubes were wood made moulds, 33 grade Agni OPC cement, Trowels, and Tamping rods.

The dimensions of moulds were measured by using the Vernier Caliper. About 200 g cement and 600 g sand mixed in accordance with standard gradation used for masonry purpose mortar in the mix ratio 1:3 were taken.

The cement and sand were mixed with trowel for 1 minute and water was added. The amount of water to be added was calculated as $(p/4+3) \%$, where p is the percent water required to produce the paste of standard consistency which ranges from 25-30 for Portland cement. Immediately after mixing the mortar, it was placed in a cube mold of 0.005 m² surface area and was prodded by using tamping rods. Then the cube mold was placed in temperature of about 20-25 degree Celsius and 90 percent humidity for 24 hours. After 24 hours the cube was taken out (Fig. 3), measured and immediately placed in clean water till testing. After 7 and 28 days, the cubes were loaded in the unconfined compression testing machine to determine compressive strength of the mortar cubes (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 Sample preparation for Mortar test

Fig. 4 Mortar cube compressive strength test

2.3 Local Geology of the Study Area

The local scale boundaries of the previously prepared map by [14] were transferred to the topographic map of scale 1:25000 (Fig. 5). The Kamala Tawa Thrust (KTT) divides overall Siwaliks into the inner and outer belts. Within the local area, only the Upper Siwalik Subgroup of the outer belt is exposed. It consists of coarse boulder conglomerates with irregular bands and lenses of sandstone and thin intercalation of yellow, brown grey silt-shale. Most of the sampling points falls within the inner belt. The Lower Siwalik Subgroup consists of fine-grained, hard, grey sandstones interbedded with purple and brown shales. The lower part of the Middle Siwalik Subgroup consists of fine- to medium-grained sandstone with interbeds of greenish gray siltstone and subordinate mudstone. The upper part of the Middle Siwalik Subgroup consists of medium- to coarse-grained sandstones and pebbly sandstones with siltstone and mudstone flasers [21].

Fig. 5 Local Geological map with sampling points (After DMG, 2005)

3. Results

3.1 Grading

Various gradation types ranging from uniform to well graded particle size gradations can be found on the samples with fineness modulus value ranging from 1.35 to 3.31 showing various types of sands (Table 3). Most of the river sand does not fit into the limits of general purpose mortar due to its coarse nature (Fig. 6). All the crushed sands fit into the limits of general purpose mortar due to its fine- to medium-frained nature (Fig. 7). Most of the river sand grading fits into the limits of floor screeding (Fig. 8) and most of the crushed-rock sand grading does not fit into the limits of floor screeding (Fig. 9). Both the river sand (Fig. 10) and the crushed-rock sand gradings fit into the limits of internal plastering and external rendering (Fig. 11).

Fig. 6. River sand comparison curves for general purpose mortar (Designation BS: 1299 (1984))

Fig. 7. Crushed-rock sand comparison curves for general purpose mortar (Designation BS: 1299 (1984))

Fig. 8 River sand comparison curves for floor screeding (Benning field (1980))

Fig. 9. Crushed-rock sand comparison curves for floor screeding (Benningfield (1980))

Fig. 10. River sand comparison curves for external rendering and plastering BS: 1199 (1986)

Fig. 11. Crushed-rock sand comparison curves for external rendering and plastering (BS: 1199 (1986))

Table 3: Sieve analysis results

Sample no.	Coefficient of uniformity	Coefficient of curvature	Grading type	Finness modulus	Type of sand
NS1 (Trijuga)	2.5	1.1	Uniform	2.31	Medium Sand
NS2 (Trijuga)	2.1	1.0	Uniform	2.35	Medium Sand
NS3 (Trijuga)	4.4	1.0	Well graded	3.11	Coarse Sand
NS4 (Baruwa)	2.5	0.9	Uniform	2.53	Medium Sand
NS5 (Trijuga)	4.4	1.0	Well graded	3.03	Medium Sand
NS6 (Trijuga)	4.1	1.1	Well graded	3.02	Medium Sand
NS7 (Trijuga)	3.7	1.1	Well graded	3.25	Coarse Sand
NS8 (Baruwa)	4.2	1.1	Well graded	2.98	Medium Sand
NS9 (Baruwa)	3.5	0.9	Well graded	3.31	Coarse Sand
NS10 (Baruwa)	3.8	1.2	Well graded	3.22	Coarse Sand
CS1	3.3	1.2	Uniform	1.86	Fine sand
CS2	3.1	1.0	Gap graded	1.90	Fine sand
CS3	3.1	1.3	Uniform	2.11	Fine sand
CS4	2.8	1.1	Uniform	1.43	Very Fine Sand
CS5	4.2	0.8	Well graded	1.98	Fine sand
CS6	2.4	1.0	Uniform	1.53	Fine sand
CS7	4.2	1.1	Well graded	1.72	Fine sand
CS8	2.2	1.1	Uniform	1.35	Very Fine Sand
CS9	3.7	1.1	Well graded	2.10	Fine sand
CS10	3.5	1.4	Uniform	2.36	Medium Sand

3.2 Shape and surface features

Average sphericity value of particles ranges from 0.45 to 0.97 with increasing values showing closeness of the grain to the sphere. Average sphericity of the river sands varies from 0.74 to 0.79 with NS6 having maximum value and NS1 having minimum value, and crushed-rock sands from 0.73 to 0.82 with CS8 having minimum and CS4 having maximum values. Distribution of average sphericity values for river sand (Fig. 12a) and for the crushed-rock sand (Fig. 12b) is uniform. Mean roundness value ranges from 0 to 5 with increasing values showing more rounded grains of sand. Mean roundness of the river sands varies from 2.9 to 4 with NS1 having maximum value and NS10 having minimum value. Mean roundness of the crushed-rock sands varies from 2.1 to 2.6 with CS10 having maximum value and CS8 having minimum value. River sand consists of more sub rounded to sub angular particles (Fig. 13a) whereas crushed-rock sand consists of more angular and very angular particles (Fig. 13b).

Fig. 12. Average sphericity of (a) River sand and (b) Crushed-rock sand.

Fig. 13 Roundness of (a) River sand and (b) Crushed-rock sand.

Blade particles, which remain roughly 50%, are the most abundant among the four forms of particles in the river sands (Fig. 14a), and is followed by disc (20-35%), rod (10-20%), and equant particles (10-15%). In case of crushed-rock sands, relatively wide ranges of variations of individual form are obtained (Fig. 14b). Blade is the dominant form ((40-55%), which is followed by disc (15-45%), rod (5-25%) and equant (10-20%). In both the river sands and the crushed-rock sands, blade form is the most abundant, and is followed by disc, rod and equant forms of particles. Bladed particles are slightly more in river sands than in the crushed-rock sands, whereas disc and equant particles are slightly in excess in the

crushed-rock sands compared to those in the river sands. Surface texture consists of the texture of grains of sand of both the river sand and the crushed-rock sand. Most of the river sand consists of slightly rough to rough particles and the crushed-rock sand consists of rough to very rough particles.

3.3 Composition

3.3.1 Major Constituents

Majority of the river sand (Fig. 15a) and the crushed-rock sand (Fig. 15b) consists of quartz, feldspar, rock fragments, mica and heavy minerals (Table 4). Quartz is the dominant constituent (35-55%) in the river sands and is followed by metamorphic rock fragments (30-55%), feldspar, micas, sedimentary rock fragments, and minor constituents (Table 4). In case of the crushed-rock sands, sedimentary rock fragments, which range from 50-80%, are the dominant constituent since the crushed-rock sands are derived after crushing sandstones. This is followed by quartz, mica, feldspar, and the remaining constituents (Table 4).

Table 4 : Composition of grains in sand

Sample Number	Composition					
	Qz	Fe	Mi	Rs	Ms	Heavies
NS1 (Trijuga)	52.50	9.50	3.70	0.80	32.08	1.25
NS2 (Trijuga)	49.50	7.50	6.60	3.70	31.60	0.83
NS3 (Trijuga)	35.00	3.30	6.00	5.60	47.60	2.30
NS4 (Baruwa)	51.60	2.91	9.58	2.91	31.25	1.60
NS5 (Trijuga)	49.16	1.60	5.80	5.40	37.50	0.40
NS6 (Trijuga)	52.50	5.80	5.40	4.10	31.60	0.40
NS7 (Trijuga)	39.00	2.30	6.00	6.30	44.60	1.67
NS8 (Baruwa)	42.91	2.50	3.30	5.80	44.10	1.25
NS9 (Baruwa)	44.10	2.50	8.30	2.50	41.20	1.25
NS10 (Baruwa)	37.08	4.50	5.00	2.90	47.50	2.91
CS1	24.80	9.30	12.80	50.20	-	2.70
CS2	27.08	5.41	15.80	50.83	-	0.83
CS3	30.00	2.64	10.50	55.73	-	1.13
CS4	18.50	2.70	8.49	67.23	1.15	1.93
CS5	17.03	3.70	8.14	69.62	-	1.48
CS6	21.70	2.40	6.50	68.20	-	1.03
CS7	18.60	2.00	6.00	72.00	-	1.30
CS8	17.00	5.60	2.70	74.00	-	0.70
CS9	16.30	2.00	4.30	76.00	-	1.30
CS10	18.30	4.00	6.30	70.30	0.70	0.30

Qz*: Quartz, Fe*: Feldspar, Mi*: Mica, Rs* Sedimentary rock fragment,

Rm*: Metamorphic rock fragment, Heavies*: Heavy minerals

Fig. 14. Form of particles in (a) River sand and (b) Crushed-rock sand

Fig. 15 Composition of particles in (a) River sand and (b) Crushed-rock sand

3.3.2 Deleterious constituents

Deleterious constituents in sand consists of the percentage of fines (<0.075 mm), mica percentage, friable particles, clay lumps, organic matter which negatively affect the workability of mortar [25]. Both the river sand and the crushed-rock sand have considerable amount of deleterious constituents, varying respectively from 4 to 11% and from 10 to 21% (Table 5). Deleterious material content in the river sand is comparatively less than that in the crushed rock sand (Table 5). Most of the grains of sand in the crushed rock sand is red coated due to iron as a result of weathering and some of the grains in the river sand is also iron coated. Iron coating ranges from 2.99 to 4.05% in the river sand with NS1 having maximum and NS10 having minimum content. In case of the crushed-rock sand, the content varies from 6 to 17% with CS6 having maximum content and CS2 is having minimum content.

3.3.2.1 Organic Content

Organic content in the river sand varies from 0.05 to 0.51% with NS4 having maximum content and NS8 and NS10 having minimum content (Fig. 20). There is a fluctuating trend of variation of organic content among the river sands. Organic content in the crushed-rock sand varies within a narrow range from 0.8 to 1.1% with CS9 having maximum content and CS1 having minimum content (Fig. 21). Thus, organic content is greater in the crushed-rock sand than in river sand.

Table 5 Deleterious constituent of sands

Sample Number	% fines (<0.075 mm)	Mica (%)	Organic matter (%)	Others including organic debris (%)	Total (%)
NS1	1.32	3.70	0.459	0.60	9.08
NS2	0.91	6.60	0.351	0.80	8.66
NS3	1.40	6.00	0.419	0.68	8.50
NS4	0.54	9.58	0.514	0.54	8.18
NS5	0.77	5.80	0.405	0.62	7.59
NS6	0.70	5.40	0.162	0.58	6.84
NS7	1.53	6.00	0.243	0.87	7.25
NS8	0.19	3.30	0.054	0.65	4.19
NS9	0.37	8.30	0.270	0.78	3.72
NS10	0.74	5.00	0.054	0.87	3.66
CS1	4.55	12.80	0.486	0.58	18.42
CS2	3.55	15.80	0.676	0.78	20.81
CS3	3.53	10.50	0.757	0.25	15.04
CS4	5.08	8.49	0.730	0.65	14.95
CS5	6.05	8.14	0.622	0.47	15.29
CS6	5.63	6.50	0.703	0.82	13.65
CS7	7.16	6.00	0.784	0.75	14.69
CS8	6.60	2.70	0.649	0.67	10.62
CS9	4.24	4.30	0.811	0.57	9.92
CS10	4.53	6.30	0.595	0.74	12.16

Table 6 Physical properties of sand

Sample Number	Saturated surface dry specific gravity (g/cm ³)	Dry Specific Gravity (g/cm ³)	Apparent Specific gravity (g/cm ³)	Water absorption (%)
NS1	2.488	2.377	2.674	3.448
NS2	2.766	2.735	2.822	5.971
NS3	2.611	2.534	2.747	4.675
NS4	2.502	2.364	2.742	5.820
NS5	2.761	2.723	2.831	4.540
NS6	2.693	2.622	2.821	2.306
NS7	2.432	2.326	2.601	1.136
NS8	2.579	2.521	2.677	3.067
NS9	2.489	2.349	2.732	1.397
NS10	2.574	2.488	2.721	2.684
CS1	2.153	1.838	2.682	7.123
CS2	2.336	2.201	2.544	6.130
CS3	2.060	1.741	2.556	8.330
CS4	2.045	1.752	2.477	6.708
CS5	2.268	2.139	2.457	6.054
CS6	2.316	2.098	2.683	10.377
CS7	2.129	1.905	2.457	11.798
CS8	2.299	2.072	2.682	10.963
CS9	2.324	2.104	2.698	10.476
CS10	2.366	2.229	2.582	6.127

3.4 Physical Properties

Saturated surface dry specific gravity (G_{SSD}) of the river sand varies from 2.4 to 2.7 and the crushed-rock sand from 2.1 to 2.3. Dry specific gravity (G_{Dry}) of river sand varies from 2.3 to 2.7 and crushed-rock sand from 1.7 to 2.2. Apparent specific gravity (G_{SA}) of river sand varies from 2.6 to 2.8 and crushed-rock sand from 2.4 to 2.6. Water absorption of the river sand varies from 1.1 to 5.9 percent and the crushed-rock sand from 6.0 to 11% (Table 6). Water absorption (WA) of the river sand is quite less compared to the crushed-rock sand.

3.5 Mortar Cube Test

Performance analysis of mortar cubes consists of various useful parameters of UCS of the river sand (Fig. 16a) and the crushed-rock sand (Fig. 16b) in 7 and 28 days of curing. Crushed-rock sand gives slightly low strength in 7 days of

curing the mortar cube. Seven days UCS of river sand mortar cube ranges from 2 to 11 Mpa. In the case of crushed-rock sand mortar cubes, the UCS ranges from 3 to 7 Mpa.

Fig. 16 Unconfined compressive test results of (a) River sand and (b) Crushed-rock sand.

3.6 Evaluation of river sand and crushed rock sand

The parameters used for evaluating the quality of sand are grading, water absorption, deleterious constituents and organic content. Taking BS standard as a reference for grading, it can be stated that most of the river sands except NS1, NS2 and NS4 are not suitable for general purpose mortar but all the crushed-rock sands are suitable for the use in general purpose mortar. Among all the samples only NS4, NS6 and NS8 and most of the crushed-rock sand except CS10 are suitable for use in floor screeding purposes. All the natural river sand samples except CS6 and CS8 are suitable for plastering and rendering purposes. Specific gravity of 2.5 to 3.0 is mainly used in construction. All the river sand are suitable for construction purposes. CS2, CS3 and CS5 are not suitable according to specific gravity specification. According to BS 812-2, water absorption of fine aggregates should not exceed 3%. This specification makes NS6, NS7, NS8, NS9 and NS10 suitable among all the river sands and crushed-rock sands. According to BS 882, maximum limit for mica content 8%. This specification makes all the river sand suitable except NS4 and NS9. In case of the crushed sand only CS6, CS7, CS8, CS9 and CS10 are suitable for mortar considering only mica percentage.

According to ASTM C 33/ C33M -13, the maximum limit for fines is 3 %. Limits for fines content in the crushed rock sand is more than in the river sand. All the river sand are suitable for construction with respect to fine content but within 3% limit, all the crushed-rock sand are not suitable for construction. According to C33/ C33M-13, the maximum limit for organic content is 1%. This specification makes all the river sand suitable for construction. In case of the Crushed-rock sand except CS3, CS4, CS7 and CS9 all the crushed-rock sands are suitable for construction. All the governing parameters determining the suitability is summarized in Table 7.

3.7 Discussion

Grading analysis from sieve analysis data gives result about the particle size distribution of various samples collected from the site. Most of the river sand are well graded. The particle size of river sand samples depends on the erosional pattern of river. Most of the crushed-rock sands, which are crushed using pestle by hand are uniform graded. The particle size distribution of crushed-rock sand depends on crushing mechanism. Most of the river sands are not suitable

for general purpose mortar due to coarse- to very coarse-grained nature of other samples. All the river sand samples are suitable for plastering and rendering purposes because of large acceptance of grading requirement in plastering and rendering. All the crushed-rock sands, due to their fine nature, are suitable for general purpose mortar. All samples except CS10 are suitable for floor screeding purposes, which needs medium-grained sand samples. The data shows that crushed sands are more suitable for general purpose mortars, and river sands are more suitable for plastering and rendering purposes. Water absorption values of NS1, NS2, NS3, NS4, and NS5 are greater due to presence of more fines and NS6, NS7, NS8, NS9 and NS10 are smaller due to less concentration of fines. Crushed sand due to greatest concentration of fines have higher water absorption values. The values of percent fines with water absorption does not completely correlate with each other but with some pattern greater the fines content more the water absorption values. Organic content in the river sand is lower in the upstream portions of the river. NS8, NS9, NS10 have less contents due to less intervention of human wastes and NS1, NS2, NS3, NS4 have more contents due to more human intervention in the downstream portions of the river. Due to presence of fossils and carbons in the sandstone of the Siwalik Group, organic content becomes slightly higher in the crushed-rock sands.

Specific gravity of the natural river sand are more than specific gravity of the crushed-rock sand, because of more organic matter contents in the crushed rock sand. Mortar cube compressive strengths of most of the river sand samples containing more fines are greater than those containing less amount of fines. Seven days compressive strength of the crushed-rock sand is comparatively lower than that of the river sand due to lower compaction and more setting time for the crushed rock sand.

3.8 Conclusion

Most of the river sands are of medium- to coarse-grained nature and most of the crushed-rock sands are of very fine- to fine-grained nature. River sands are not suitable for general purpose mortar but all the crushed-rock sand are suitable for it. Most of both river sands and crushed-rock sands are suitable for plastering and rendering purposes, whereas only few are suitable for floor screeding. Specific gravity values of the river sands are slightly greater than that of the crushed-rock sands, but both types of sands fall in to the acceptable range for using in mortar. Water absorption values are quite more for the crushed-rock sand than the river sand. Most of the sand samples are out of the range of standard water absorption value.

In the case of shape of sand grains, both sand types possess similar average sphericity values, but the crushed rock sands are more angular compared to the river sands. Both sands have bladed, disc, prolate and equant in decreasing abundance. Proportion of disc and equant slightly exceeds in the crushed rock sands than in the river sands. Quartz and metamorphic rock fragments are two most abundant constituents of the river sand, whereas quartz and sedimentary rock fragments are abundant in the crushed rock sand. Organic content tests give acceptable range for use in mortar from both sands. River sand consists of relatively less organic matter than the crushed rock sand. Due to the presence of more fines and organic content, the crushed rock sand consists of more deleterious constituents than the river sand.

The mortar cubes from the river sand give better results in 7-days test of UCS compared to that by the crushed-rock sands, but the mortar cubes from the crushed-rock sands performed more well after 28-days of curing. All these specific and performance tests on both the river sands and the crushed-rock sands reveal their engineering properties and suggest that with some treatment and beneficiation process of reducing fines and organic matter, the crushed rock sands can be used as an alternative for the river sands. In using the crushed-rock sands made from sandstones, screening of fines and organic matter are necessary for its optimum use. Tests after screening and washing of the crushed-rock sands are also recommended as most of the deleterious constituents are removed after washing.

Table 7 Evaluation of sands consisting of governing parameters for mortar

Sample number	Gradation analysis			Specific gravity (gm/cm ³)	Deleterious constituents (%)	Organic matter (%)	Water absorption (%)	Mica (%)
	General purpose	Floor screeding	Plastering and rendering					
NS1	✓		✓	2.674	6.080	0.459	3.448	3.7
NS2	✓		✓	2.822	8.660	0.351	5.971	6.6
NS3			✓	2.747	8.500	0.419	4.675	6
NS4	✓	✓	✓	2.742	11.170	0.514	5.82	9.58
NS5			✓	2.831	7.590	0.405	4.54	5.8
NS6		✓	✓	2.821	6.840	0.162	2.306	5.4
NS7			✓	2.601	8.650	0.243	1.136	6
NS8		✓	✓	2.677	4.190	0.054	3.067	3.3
NS9			✓	2.732	9.720	0.27	1.397	8.3
NS10			✓	2.721	6.660	0.054	2.684	5
CS1	✓		✓	2.674	18.690	0.486	17.123	12.8
CS2	✓		✓	2.822	21.080	0.676	6.13	15.8
CS3	✓		✓	2.747	15.310	0.757	8.33	10.5
CS4	✓		✓	2.742	15.220	0.73	6.708	8.49
CS5	✓		✓	2.831	15.560	0.622	6.054	8.14
CS6	✓			2.821	13.920	0.703	10.377	6.5
CS7	✓		✓	2.601	14.960	0.784	11.798	6
CS8	✓			2.677	10.890	0.649	10.963	2.7
CS9	✓		✓	2.732	10.190	0.811	10.476	4.3
CS10	✓	✓	✓	2.721	12.430	0.595	6.127	6.3

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